

MARINEWIND

Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology Systems (FOWTs)

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T1.3_Spain Lab 1st Co-creation Workshop Report

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Roses, Catalonia

EVENT DATE: 25th October 2023 (from 9.30 AM to 2.30 PM)

EVENT TITLE: OFFSHORE WIND IN L'EMPORDÀ

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: European Maritime Day

LEAD ORGANISER: Sener

CO-ORGANISERS: -

LANGUAGE: Spanish and Catalan

CONCEPT

The Spanish 1st Co-creation workshop had a primary focus on the latest advancements in Floating Offshore Wind Technologies in Spain. This event was closely associated with the Horizon Europe project MARINEWIND, which is financially supported by the European Commission. To be more specific, the workshop took place at the *Casal de Pescadors* (Fishermen's house) in Roses, a town situated in the L'Empordà region, and this location was chosen due to its proximity to the only high-potential area for using floating offshore wind technology in Catalonia.

The workshop was divided into two main parts. The first part featured 11 representatives from the 5-helix stakeholders who delivered presentations on the subject. Following this, the second part involved a debate where all participants could engage in discussions. Both segments of the workshop provided a valuable opportunity for in-depth conversations about various aspects and differing perspectives regarding the implementation of offshore wind energy in the L'Empordà region. We were fortunate to have participants with diverse viewpoints on this important matter.

OBJECTIVES To discuss barriers and facilitators to offshore wind deployment in Spain, and specifically in L'Empordà (Catalonia).

TARGET AUDIENCE: The participation included representatives of the 5-Helix stakeholders' groups:

- Industry: FOWT installation developers, engineering companies, fisheries, local traders, etc.
- Civil Society: civil society organisations, renewable organisations, etc.
- Academia: scientific community and public/private research organisations.
- Public Authorities: Spanish, Catalanian, and local government.
- Green Innovation: ecologists, environmental organisations and green cooperatives.

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT: 40 participants

Figure 1 Participants overview.

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

The choice of speakers was made with the intention of ensuring a balanced representation of the 5-helix stakeholders. Furthermore, the speakers' participation was organized into four distinct categories:

2.1 Exploring the perspectives of various administrations, assessing the current regulatory framework, and discussing the energy landscape in Catalonia.

Agustí Badosa, Sant Pere Pescador Town Hall

Agustí Badosa highlights the importance of setting clear, minimum conditions for offshore wind projects, all while recognizing the immense potential that harnessing the wind resource of the "Tramuntana" holds for the region. However, he raises significant concerns, primarily centered on the potential adverse effects on tourism, the visual landscape, and marine ecosystems. Badosa strongly emphasizes the need for ensuring safety and minimizing these potential impacts, suggesting the utilization of testing platforms like PLEMCAT¹ (R+D+i Platform for Marine Energies of Catalonia). Furthermore, he advocates for compensation to be provided for all sectors that may be affected by these developments. Badosa places a great deal of emphasis on the Govern of Catalonia's pivotal role and urges it to adopt a more active stance, given its potential significance in this matter. He also acknowledges the pressing issue of the climate emergency and underscores the region's responsibility to take action.

Assumpta Ferran, Managing Director for Energy of the Catalan Government

Assumpta Ferran underlines the importance of offshore wind energy projects, driven by the climate emergency. She reflects on the urgent need to act quickly, as she considers that too much time has been wasted by the Catalan institutions. Reflecting on Catalonia's initial foray into offshore wind in 2010, in particular the project Zéfir in l'Atmetlla de Mar² which was cancelled due to public opposition, Ferran regrets the missed opportunity. She now expresses concern about the slow pace of investment and administrative processes in the energy sector, and advocates for the simplification of procedures.

Ferran focuses on safeguarding the sea, considering it a finite resource and stressing the importance of preserving its biodiversity. She also affirms the immediate need for action, highlighting the grid connection planned for PLEMCAT and stressing that it must be an absolute priority.

Ferran considers the 2030 energy targets to be unambitious and explores the potential of offshore wind farms to serve as electricity interconnection points between states, drawing inspiration from

¹ [PLEMCAT - IREC](#) will offer a floating platform in the Mediterranean Sea that will include different areas to develop the validation of these activities and tests:

1. Area for the evaluation of materials and components to understand and identify their behaviour in real marine conditions and area for other R&D&I activities.
2. Area for testing prototypes of marine energy generation technologies with positions of up to 18 MW.
3. Area for validation of pre-commercial wind generation technologies with long-term permanence.

² ZÉFIR Project. Around 2012, the regional government of Catalonia (Generalitat de Catalunya) and IREC promoted Zéfir project. In the first phase of the Zéfir project, 4 fixed offshore wind turbines will be located between the Cambrils and L'Ametlla de Mar area, with an installed capacity of 10 to 20 MW, at a distance of 3.5 km from the coast and at a depth of around 35 m. In the second phase of the Zéfir project, 8 floating offshore wind turbines with an installed capacity of 50 MW, at a distance of 30 km from the coast and at a depth of about 100 meters. This project was cancelled due to, amongst other, local opposition.

France's proactive initiatives in pre-commercial projects. She calls for international coordination between states to ensure the orderly deployment of offshore wind energy. She concludes by stressing the collective responsibility to act quickly and collaboratively.

Juan Ramón Ayuso, director of Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (Spanish Institution)

Juan Ramón Ayuso is dedicated to fortifying the development of floating wind power in Spain, driven by both economic and energy imperatives. He has delineated qualitative goals within the Offshore Wind Roadmap, with a focus on consolidating technology and nurturing the domestic market to bolster the value chain. Concurrently, he is actively involved in shaping a legislative framework that harmonizes with environmental considerations and encourages greater investment. Ayuso's message underscores the paramount importance of social and environmental sustainability as a means to surmount entrenched positions. He recognizes the pivotal role of initial projects in establishing industry standards, with a particular emphasis on collaborating with local economies and optimizing synergies to integrate into the regional economic landscape. Ayuso prioritizes environmental awareness, understanding the marine environment and its biodiversity, leveraging this knowledge to expand horizons. He places a strong emphasis on the coexistence of diverse activities within these projects and actively advocates for positive arguments from a social perspective.

2.2 Delving into the environmental aspects of offshore wind power and examining citizen engagement in the field.

Pep Puig, ecologist and promoter of collective onshore wind project “Viure de l’aire”

Pep Puig advocates the defence of offshore wind energy, highlighting the crucial role of citizen collaboration. He stresses the importance of using local resources without damaging the environment, which in his opinion is he has never seen any wind power project that has harmed any ecosystem. He gives the example of an offshore wind farm in Denmark, highlighting citizen cooperation, compatibility and its attractiveness for tourism. In that project, the developer offered shares in the wind farm to the public, fostering a sense of ownership and partnership with the local community.

Adrián Bautista, CEO and co-founder at Fundeen³

Adrián Bautista stresses that in order to involve the general public in renewable energy projects, the role of crowdfunding companies is crucial. He stresses that, although there is no legal obligation, the social aspect of these projects is vital for their success and public acceptance. He believes that managing this social aspect effectively is key. Bautista's central idea is to turn the local community into enthusiastic promoters of the project. To do this, he suggests allowing citizens to fund at least 20% of the project, fostering a "sense of ownership". It is essential that project promoters establish a presence in the community during the early stages of the project.

Bautista also stresses the importance of extensive communication and public participation, while offering incentives from project promoters. He believes that in the face of a position against offshore wind development, a choice must be made between two scenarios: the visual changes brought about

³ <https://www.fundeen.com/> Fundeen is a platform for co-investment in renewable energy projects and is an agent for change in the European energy model.

by renewable energy installations or the visual transformations resulting from climate change and desertification. Given that the current situation is often being compared with the future situation of an offshore wind farm, when if we do not act quickly, the current world will no longer exist.

2.3 Analyzing the effects on diverse sectors influenced by this technology.

Pere Gotanegra, Fishermen of Roses⁴ and Peixos Gotanegra companies

Pere Gotanegra, as a local businessman, expresses his support for offshore wind energy, while strongly condemning the aggressive disinformation campaign about Parc Tramuntana (Offshore wind farm in front of Roses, Catalonia, promoted by Bluefloat Energy and Sener Renewable Investment). He stresses the importance of dedicating resources and providing accurate information to the local residents. Gotanegra firmly believes that if citizens are fully aware of the project, they are less likely to reject its implementation. He underlines the overall objective of seeking the common good for the region, stressing the need for a collaborative approach that benefits the whole community.

Koldo Díez-Caballero, marine operations manager in Tecnoambiente

Koldo Díez-Caballero places special emphasis on the overall process of preparing environmental impact studies, which involves a wide range of data, requirements and considerations covering physical, socio-economic, biological and environmental aspects. He stresses the crucial role of public participation in these studies and the need to assess both the risks and opportunities associated with these projects from an environmental point of view, with the aim of preserving and gaining a better understanding of the local ecosystem. He considers these projects to be a valuable source of real data for analysis, especially in the context of offshore wind energy deployment. Díez-Caballero gives as an example the assessment of the impact of offshore wind farms on birds and concludes that the risk is generally low.

Díez-Caballero points out that most impacts are accompanied by elimination and mitigation measures and, failing that, there are mechanisms to compensate those affected. He also stresses the importance of involving various social actors, including the fisheries sector, to facilitate citizen participation and address any concerns or questions related to offshore wind initiatives.

Antoni Abad, chairman of roses fishermen's association

Antoni Abad's main concern is to protect the hake population in a restricted area to ensure the livelihood of fishermen in the Bay of Roses. This restricted zone was an initiative of the Fishermen's Guild more than 10 years ago, and he firmly believes that the Roses Guild is in danger if the offshore wind farm (offshore wind project near Roses) is not executed correctly. Abad insists that offshore wind projects should be carried out responsibly, even if this means a slight delay: "if we are already late, there is no point in doing it quickly and badly".

Specifically for the zoning proposed by the State for offshore wind in Catalonia, he highlights the obligation of fishing boats to sail around offshore wind farms, if not open corridors through the middle of the park. This translates into higher fuel costs and longer travel times to the fishing grounds. In

⁴ Pescadors de Roses Planta Envasat SL is a company created by the Cofradía de Pescadors de Roses and the company Peixos Gotanegra SL

addition, there are concerns about the economic sustainability of the local fishing sector and the compatibility of fishing with offshore wind energy. Therefore, he also values positively those projects that ensure that these issues will be taken into consideration. In summary, Abad recognizes the need for these projects, but stresses the importance of thoroughly considering their impacts, rather than rushing them without due diligence.

2.4 Emphasizing the contributions of academia, industry, and research platforms in the offshore wind energy domain.

Jose Luis Domínguez, representing IREC (Energy Research Institute of Catalonia Foundation), promoter of PLEMCAT

José Luis Domínguez insists on the need for complete environmental data to properly deploy offshore wind and underlines the valuable value of a test platform such as PLEMCAT for this purpose. The platform will be able to test not only floating platforms for WTG of commercial size, but also materials testing and more.

Dominguez also points out that currently climate change-induced changes in water temperature could negatively affect local species. In fact, he argues that these species may face extinction in the coming years if nothing is done to combat climate change. He believes it is important to put the potential impact of offshore wind farms in context for this purpose, and to assess it properly.

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Sergi Ametller, director of Offshore Wind in Sener and CEO of HiveWind⁵

Sergi Ametller, as the visible face of Parc Tramuntana⁶ in the area, acknowledges the prevailing negative perceptions about offshore wind projects and stresses the importance of addressing them effectively. He emphasizes the project's commitment to ensuring compatibility with the fishing industry, with the aim of achieving harmonious coexistence. It also emphasizes the project's compatibility with biodiversity and the local ecosystem, with measures to minimize ecological impact.

⁵ [Hive Wind Energy | Best Future Of Energy | Modular Future - 2023](#) Hive Wind Energy S.L. is a company established with capital from Sener Renewable Investments, a company of the Sener engineering and technology group, and the Amper group, through its subsidiary Nervión Naval-Offshore. It is a semi-submersible floating steel foundation for wind turbine with power ratings above 15 MW which bases its design on the ease of manufacture and a high degree of standardization of the construction elements.

⁶ [Parc Tramuntana](#) Proposal for a floating offshore wind farm pending auction including 33 wind turbines and a capacity of 495MW, 24km off the Bay of Roses. Proposed by Sener Renewable Investments and BlueFloat Energy.

It considers the active participation of citizens essential, with particular attention to cultivating a sense of pride and ownership, similar to the successful approach seen in countries such as Denmark with renewable energy initiatives. With this, it would be hoped that citizens near the park would feel a sense of pride in the project being undertaken.

In addition, Ametller remarks that necessity to incorporate measures and agreements with the local community to mitigate potential negative impacts. Rigorous analysis requires scientific data and methods, which underscores the importance of obtaining objective information through, for example, Lidar buoys (with built-in sensors that provide real-time atmospheric and aquatic conditions). through the installation of PLEMCAT or projects as HiveLab⁷, 11MW demonstrator project of HiveWind.

Pere Roura, teacher at the University of Girona

Pere Roura emphasizes the inherent uncertainties in the energy transition process, acknowledging that we don't have all the answers. He highlights the potential for conflicting information and conclusions, emphasizing the need to promote and share well-founded results to combat misinformation effectively. Roura strongly supports renewable energies as the most effective means to decarbonize the economy. He also underscores the importance of achieving energy independence to reduce reliance on geopolitically complex and unstable countries. He urges that the energy transition should be seen as an opportunity rather than a threat. In this context, he encourages a focus on constructive dialogue, limiting accusations, and spreading apolitical messages to facilitate a more informed and positive approach to this critical transition. Roura centered his presentation around the intriguing idea that the energy transition can be likened to a multi-faceted polyhedron, with key facets including climatology, engineering, ecology, mineral resources, economics, territorial management, and politics. Overemphasizing any single facet can result in misinformation and hinder our advancement. Being part of a university provides a unique opportunity to address and contribute to all these aspects, thereby propelling the generation of vital information.

3 ROUNDTABLES TOPICS OVERVIEW

To facilitate the discussion, attendees' questions were used by the moderator to allow anyone, speaker or attendee, to have the chance to give their perspectives. The choice of event participants was likewise structured to ensure a fair and balanced representation of the 5-helix stakeholders. The debate went very smoothly and despite the fact that not all the registered questions were finally read, the debate flowed through very interesting topics, which will be summarised below.

The offshore wind debate in Roses covered various vital points. First and foremost, it emphasized the active involvement of the public in capital participation and the benefits of local energy consumption. However, the conversation also highlighted several barriers, including a lack of public awareness,

⁷ [HIVELAB - HiveWind \(hivewindenergy.com\)](http://hivewindenergy.com) The HIVELAB project consists of the manufacture, installation, and commissioning of a HiveWind demonstrator with a 11MW commercial turbine and a lifetime of 25 years, with the aim of testing this technology in a real marine environment during the first 2 years. Its main objectives are to demonstrate the viability of the HiveWind concept, to enhance the supply chain, to gain knowledge on the environmental impact (with the use of several sensors), to evaluate and promote the compatibility with other activities (such as fishing, tourism or aquaculture), to evaluate the impact of auxiliary elements on biodiversity regeneration using regenerative eco-structures and to maximize the social acceptance.

uncertainty about how citizens will benefit, and concerns about the environmental impact of offshore wind projects. The debate on equity participation in offshore wind farms brought up several key points. It was noted that involving many citizens is crucial for equity participation and proximity power consumption. However, barriers such as lack of knowledge, uncertainties, and concerns about environmental impact need to be addressed. Ensuring accurate information dissemination, changing established narratives, and providing pedagogical support are essential in overcoming conservatism and encouraging a positive outlook on new technologies.

The discussion also highlighted the need to consider both the environmental impact of offshore wind farms and the impacts of climate change that are already occurring, emphasizing the urgency of addressing this issue. Access to objective environmental data, facilitated by initiatives like PLEMCAT, was seen as vital.

Social pressure and the influence of opinions in small communities can lead to negative perceptions based on ignorance. It was emphasized that the environmental impact of offshore wind farms is manageable due to strict regulatory requirements, and the dismantling process and anchor impact on the seabed should be carefully considered. The auction process was recognized as key to defining the social impact on the territory, with a call for clear and concise criteria favouring developers committed to the region. Working groups were proposed to address the role of influence in the community.

Prejudices and the fear of the unknown can lead to the rejection of new projects, highlighting the importance of minimizing uncertainties and ensuring a real positive impact on the territory. Europe was suggested as a benchmark for offshore wind projects, with PLEMCAT contributing to talent attraction and enhancing the local economy.

A call for environmental solidarity and the need for a final decision in favour of offshore wind was also raised. The debate questioned the impartial position of the Govern of Catalonia and posed the crucial question, "In whose hands do we leave our land?"

The importance of credible information, trust in government administrations, and the significance of marine research and innovation were also highlighted. Furthermore, the debate showcased the potential for Roses to become a hub for offshore wind knowledge and investment. While acknowledging the substantial investments required, the commitment to realizing the potential of offshore wind in the region remained strong.

4 CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES

To conclude the event, the Mentimeter tool was used to record the baseline questions from all Marine Wind workshops in the different locations. As it was conducted at the end of the event as conclusion of the roundtable and some participants have some doubts about the anonymity of the results, not all the participants took part.

Which of the following categories represents you?

The following graph shows how the participants and speakers were divided. 42% industry, 23% university, 15% public authorities, 8% civil society and 8% green innovation.

It is a bit different from the real map we had from the organisation, if everybody had participated (32% industry, 26% civil society, 16% academia, 13% public authorities and 13% green innovation)

Figure 2 MENTIMETER. Question 1

What are the most important enablers for investing in floating offshore wind?

The survey results show that a significant majority of respondents prefer a well-defined regulatory framework. This aligns with an earlier theme discussed in the debate. The next most important factors are technological maturity, the availability of incentives, and a substantial market share and demand. In contrast, stability of the transmission grid and the potential for local supply chain development received minimal support, with only one vote each.

Figure 3 MENTIMETER. Question 2

In your opinion, where is the most significant risk in the supply chain?

Regarding the most significant supply chain risk, the responses show a very close alignment between concerns about sufficient infrastructure development and the capacity of the local supply chain. In comparison, the availability of ad hoc vessels for turbine installation is seen as a lesser concern.

Figure 4 MENTIMETER. Question 3

Which activity is most in conflict with the offshore wind sector?

The majority of respondents believe that fishing is currently the primary activity in conflict with offshore wind deployment. This is followed by concerns about environmental protection. Tourism, on the other hand, received a comparatively lower number of votes as a conflicting activity.

Figure 5 MENTIMETER. Question 4

Which activity is most compatible with floating offshore wind?

In terms of activities considered most compatible with the deployment of floating offshore wind, respondents ranked tourism and shipping as the most compatible. Environmental protection came next, followed by fishing and various other activities.

Figure 6 MENTIMETER. Question 5

What other aspects not mentioned above do you think should be taken into account for the development of offshore wind energy?

- Public Acceptance and Engagement: Ensuring the support and active participation of citizens.
- Training and Education: Providing education and skill development.
- Environmental Impact and Local Economies: Assessing how offshore wind projects affect the environment and local economies.
- Local Economic Growth: Focusing on enhancing economic development within the region.
- Turbine Manufacturing: Considering the environmental impacts and potential for reusing materials.
- Trade-offs: Evaluating the pros and cons of different choices.
- Attention to Fishermen: Recognizing the significant impact on the fishing community and their specific needs.
- Citizen-Centric Laws: Enacting legislation that factors in citizen participation and their territorial vision.
- Collaborative Working Groups: Establishing joint efforts among all affected parties for awareness and dissemination.
- Green Procurement Promotion: Encouraging institutions to support environmentally friendly purchasing.
- Energy Security and Independence: Addressing the need for energy security and self-sufficiency.
- Local Socio-Economic Benefits: Highlighting the visibility of benefits at the local level and emphasizing best practices.
- Global Best Practices: Learning from and implementing successful approaches at a global or European scale.
- Ongoing Environmental and Social Impact Monitoring: Continuous assessment and improvement.
- Secure Development Timelines: Ensuring stable planning and investments for logistical requirements and local industrial positioning.
- Renewable Energy Policies: Implementing regulations for self-consumption in companies of a certain size.

- **Workforce Training:** Developing qualified workers and educating society.
- **National Planning and Clarity:** Having a clear and well-defined national plan.
- **Administrative Efficiency:** Streamlining administrative processes.
- **Raising Public Awareness:** Educating the population about the value of the offshore wind industry and its connection to the sea.
- **Pedagogy and Credibility:** Emphasizing the importance of information, context within energy globalization, and system credibility.
- **Cumulative Impact Analysis:** Developing methodologies to assess cost-benefit cumulative effects of offshore wind development.
- **Ocean Planning:** Recognizing that an ocean plan encompasses more than a map; it's a system of decision-making and priorities.

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The 1st of the three co-creation workshops for T1.3 with regards to the Offshore Wind in L'Empordà Lab has been mainly dedicated to barriers perceived by the stakeholders for the investment on FOWTs, and to potential enablers. Thanks to the data collected, the next two workshops will then focus on solutions and policies to ease the installation of Offshore Wind Plants. The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the workshop on one side, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the other.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
<p>Lack of knowledge: many people is not fully informed about the technology and benefits of offshore wind. This can generate unfounded fears or scepticism about its effectiveness and safety.</p>	<p>Public education campaigns: Conduct informational campaigns to raise public awareness about the benefits and safety of offshore wind energy.</p> <p>Outreach events: Organize workshops, lectures, and visits to offshore wind farms to allow people to learn firsthand.</p>
<p>Credibility of developers and public authorities: concerns about transparency, integrity, and the capabilities of these stakeholders can hinder industry progress.</p>	<p>Transparency and accountability: Developers and authorities should be transparent in their processes and outcomes, which can enhance trust.</p> <p>Public participation: Involve the community in decision-making and provide opportunities for public feedback.</p>
<p>Cultural heritage: The placement of offshore wind farms in areas with significant cultural or historical value can generate resistance. Opposition to the alteration of landscapes or important cultural sites can be a significant barrier.</p>	<p>Select solutions for offshore wind farms that minimize the impact on significant cultural sites. For example, use of buried lines close to houses, instead of aerial ones.</p>

<p>Visual impact: The presence of offshore wind turbines in the sea can alter the coastal landscape and have a negative visual impact on the surrounding areas. This can trigger opposition from local communities and interest groups.</p>	<p>Raise awareness that this visual impact will be much less than the possible impact left by not carrying out renewable installations (climate change effects).</p>
<p>Impact on fisheries: The installation of offshore wind farms can impact fishing, leading to resistance from local fishing communities. The loss of fishing areas or concerns about effects on marine ecosystems are important issues to consider.</p>	<p>Compensation and collaboration: Establish compensation agreements with fishing communities and collaborate in jointly managing affected areas.</p> <p>Research on coexistence: Conduct research to better understand how fishing and offshore wind energy can coexist sustainably.</p>
<p>New technology: Implementing new and emerging technologies can create uncertainty and concern about their reliability and effectiveness. The lack of a track record and experience with unproven technologies can be a barrier to adoption.</p>	<p>Pilots and trials: Conduct pilot projects and small-scale trials to demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of new technologies.</p> <p>Government support: Offer financial support and regulations that encourage the adoption of innovative technologies.</p>
<p>Environmental impact: Concerns exist about the environmental impact of the construction and operation of offshore wind farms, such as interference with marine life and ecosystems</p>	<p>Comprehensive assessment: Conduct detailed environmental impact assessments and implement effective mitigation measures to protect marine ecosystems.</p> <p>Ongoing research: Invest in scientific research to better understand and minimize environmental impact. Offshore wind technology demonstrators are a chance to increase knowledge</p>
<p>Citizen Benefits: The perception that the benefits of offshore wind energy do not reach the local population is extended.</p>	<p>It is important to effectively communicate how investment in offshore wind energy can translate into economic benefits and local employment.</p>
<p>Contrary information: The availability of conflicting information about offshore wind energy can create confusion among the public.</p>	<p>Source verification: Encourage information verification and promote reliable sources.</p> <p>Dialogue and mediation: Facilitate dialogue among stakeholders with divergent opinions and seek consensus-based solutions.</p>